

A Genetic Algorithm-Based Methodology to New Product Development

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Abstract - *The paper presents a construction and some simulations with a methodology based on genetic algorithm techniques to New Product Development problem. The objective is to show a new decision support system to help firms to cope with challenges of globalisation: contracting life cycles, high quality product, minimum time to market and flexibility to change. The research carried out points out to the exceptional possibilities of using genetic algorithm techniques in new product development.*

Keywords - Concept optimization, Voice of Customer, Multicriterion decision making, genetic algorithm.

1 Introduction

Concept optimization consists in selecting those characteristics of the product that make it more competitive from client's viewpoint. Therefore, it is necessary to use tools that allow, on one hand, to develop correct strategic politics leading to a leadership position on the market and, and on the other, to carry designers' attention to consumers' requirements. The problem is to find an adequate instrument that, analyzing the information gathered from the voice of the client (VOC) and the voice of the engineer, compares design solutions on a set of evaluation criteria.

In fact, product design involves a number of decision variables (e.g. materials, alternative components) and criteria (e.g. cost, customer satisfaction, security, risk). Moreover the goals to achieve are often in conflict (minimizing cost and maximizing customer satisfaction), rising the multicriterion decision problem.

Multicriterion problems generally involve two types of difficulties: search and multicriterion decision making. Traditionally most approaches treat these two aspects of the problem separately, and often one or the other is assumed away. Instead, the integration of search and multicriterion decision making is the key issue in AG approaches.

2 The genetic algorithm

We know genetic algorithm implementations are based on mating and reproduction mechanism, moreover several methods exist to realize these processes so the choice of using one method instead than other lays on the type of the problem in exam. Following, we show the choices made for this case, taking on that we are trying to solve a concept optimization problem.

2.1 Generation of the initial solution

The algorithm begins generating an initial population of individuals, dimension fixed in precedence.

Each individual's length is equal to the number of components of the product. Initially each chromosome possesses all the components of the product, disposed in casual manner.

2.2 Fitness function

The structure of the genetic algorithm for this kind of multicriterion problem remains the same as with single-criterion problems. The difference in this case is the fitness function. The method we chose to handle multiple criteria is to aggregate all the objectives into a single objective, which is then used to totally order the solutions. The various objectives are combined into a simple scalar-valued *utility function* $U(A)$, where $U: R^k \rightarrow R$, reflecting the multicriterion trade-offs preferences of a particular decision-maker. We used a linear combination (i.e. weighted sum) such as $U(P_j) = w_1 a_1(P_j) + w_2 a_2(P_j) + \dots + w_k a_k(P_j)$ where the w_j are constant coefficients (i.e. weights) set by the DM and P is a specific solution.

The fitness function evaluates the initial solutions basing on data contained in the first three masks. Here, functions and components were valued through different criteria (relationship matrix, importance degree, customers' evaluations, cost, environment impact, etc.); to insert all them in the fitness function we first provided a normalization of the data.

The fitness of each individual springs out from its components' evaluation. Here it is how acts the fitness function:

It assigns to each component a value $v(C_j)$, which comes out adding the normalized values of the

k evaluation criteria, $N(g_i)$:

$$v(C_j) = \sum_{i=1}^k N(g_i(C_j))$$

It assigns to each individual of the current population a fitness value (f), adding the value of all the components that constitute it:

$$f(P_j) = \sum_{i=1}^n v(C_i)$$

Until now, we didn't introduced any constrain, therefore, in this situation, the algorithm could not provide real individuals in terms of allowed cost. So we introduce the concept of feasible individual:

An individual is feasible if its total increased cost of realization, $s(P_i)$, is smaller or equal to budget constrain:

$$s(P_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n s_j(C_j) \leq \Delta B$$

This model supposes that the sum of the increased cost of all n components is greater than the budget constrain:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n s_j(C_j) > \Delta B$$

If this circumstance is not verified, the best individual would be, simply, that with all the components improved.

We are, still, working with individuals constituted by all the components, in these conditions no individual is feasible. Then, we must find a criterion that allows transforming them in feasible individuals.

We know that solutions are all the same less of the arrangement of the components, on this difference the criterion will be based. In fact, the total increased cost is calculated basing on components arrangement and, so, we decided to include in each string only those components whose cost is smaller than the budget constrain.

Also the fitness, assigned to each individual, will be calculated adding only the values of the k components that we could include:

$$f(P_i) = \sum_{j=1}^k s_j(C_j) \quad \text{with } k < n$$

In practice as we suppose that the utility grows with the number of the component present components, we could affirm that the genetic algorithm maximizes customer's utility of the given certain budget constrain.

The genetic algorithm allows us to optimize the problem avoiding exhaustive search of simple enumeration, which would result impossible for the great value that could reach n (the possible combinations would be $n!$).

2.3 Elitism

When we create a new population with crossover and mutation there is a high probability of losing the best chromosome. To avoid it, this algorithm uses the elitism mechanism. We chose the best individual, that with the highest fitness, of the current population and we will include it in the next population if it doesn't present a better one.

2.4 Selection mechanism

The individuals that will participate to reproduction are selected through roulette wheel method, discussed before. We build the roulette with cumulated fitness values, we randomly extract a number between 0 and the total cumulated fitness, we see in which sector of the wheel falls the number and so we determine the first couple. This operation is repeated so many times as the population size. In this way we select all the happy couples.

Obviously, some chromosome will have more than one copy in the intermediate population, but this is in accord with the fundamental theorem.

2.5 Crossover

The determined couples are subjected to crossover operation. Two points crossover is here used.

One of the parameters of the genetic algorithms is crossover probability p_c , this gives us the number of chromosome, $p_c * N$, which will be subjected to the operation of crossover.

This algorithm, instead of establishing a determined number for the said probability it uses a range to define it $p_c \in [p_{c1}, p_{c2}]$. Let's show the condition that each individual must satisfy to participate to crossover.

For each chromosome of intermediate population:

A number, r , is randomly generated from the range $[0 \dots 1]$.

- If, $r > \frac{p_{c1} + (p_{c2} - p_{c1}) * n^{\circ} \text{current generation}}{n^{\circ} \text{gen}}$ ft, individual, selected for

crossover, otherwise is directly withered to following phase.

The above formula assures that the number of crossover operations decreases with the generations. In fact, increasing the right part value of the formula (through *recurrent generation*) the possibilities for r to verify the condition decrease.

Once the selection process is terminated and we have randomly mated the happy couples: for each couple of chromosomes we generate two integer random number, pos_1 and pos_2 , from the range $[2 \dots l]$. These numbers point out the positions' cut.

Over time, the necessity of fewer crossover operations lays in the fact that, in first generations, we want a fast evolution (and to realize it a great information exchange between individuals is necessary), while in last generations we don't want to lose important information (therefore the information exchange must be smaller).

2.6 Mutation

This operator acts on each single gene. Another parameter of the genetic algorithm, mutation probability p_m , gives us the supposed number of genes that will change $p_m \in [p_{m1}, p_{m2}]$.

For the same reasons analyzed before, we need a decreasing mutation percentage over time. Therefore, to determine mutation probability we settle a range, $p_m \in [p_{m1}, p_{m2}]$ and we proceeded like with crossover operation.

For each chromosome of the actual population (after crossover) and for each element of the chromosome:

A number, r , is randomly generated from the range [0 ... 1].

If $r > \frac{p_{mi} + (p_{mi} - p_m) * \text{num current gen}}{n^{\circ} \text{gen}}$, the element changes.

Once this point is reached we have a new population of possible solutions, that, like initial one will be submitted to all phases described above.

This process will be repeated a number of times equal to the number of generations fixed for the algorithm.

2.1 Convergence criteria

If the genetic algorithm is correctly implemented, the population will evolve so that the fitness of the best individual and the total average in each generation grow toward the global general. The population converges when all the genes converge.

The convergence criterion is based on the number of generations. This number is settled down looking for a compromise between the time employed for the simulation and the need to reach uniformity in all population strings.

Besides, as we introduced randomly changing crossover and mutation, this avoids problems of premature convergence or slow end.

3 Description of the software model for new product

Here, we show the use of a software, based on genetic algorithms techniques, for concept optimization. Then, we will analyze the obtained results, carrying out the points of strength and of weakness of the technique proposed.

This software is programmed in Visual Basic environment, for the flexibility and for the compatibility with the Excel sheets, in which the data are generally structured.

The inputs' masks contain respectively:

- I. Relationship matrix between the functions and the components of the product.
- II. Information relative to product's functions.
- III. Information relative to product's components.
- IV. Ordering of functions and components.
- V. The implementation of the algorithm.

Following we describe more in details each single mask.

3.1 Relationships matrix \mathcal{R}_j

This mask gathers the relationship matrix, \mathcal{R}_j (See Figure 1) between the m functions and the n components and it's the main matrix of the whole system.

Figure 1. Relationship Matrix

It's necessary to create a hierarchy between the components, to distinguish their real weight between the different levels of relationships. Therefore, the matrix must inform us not only on the mere existence of relationship, but also, on their strength. To express these relationships we used five different linguistic labels, corresponding to five numerical values:

- 1: Very Weak (VW)
- 2: Weak (W)
- 3: Medium (M)
- 4: Strong (S)
- 5: Very Strong (VS)

If there is no relationship, the space will be blank, in this case the product function, corresponding to that line, is not covered by any component.

Once the matrix is filled with all the relationship, the program will pick up automatically from it the necessary information.

3.2 Functions (Fj)

The information contained in this mask is relative to product functions' characteristics.

We explain more in detail all the categories that appear:

- a) Weight of significance, WF_j : shows the significance that the interfunctional team of the firm gives to functions. A numerical scale from 1 to 5, from lesser to greater relevance, is usually established
- b) Importance, IF_j : basing on functions' weights of significance and on the values of the relationship matrix the program calculates the global importance of each function (see Figure 2).

For each line of the relationships matrix sums the corresponding values of linguistic labels and multiplies this sum for the degree of significance of the function:

$$IF_i : \sum_{>1}^n R_{ij} \times WF_i$$

c) Current evaluation, EF_i : expresses the degree of satisfaction that the customer gives to the functions supported by our actual product.

d) Target, TF_i : it is the degree of satisfaction that the customer desires to meet in the functions supported by our future product.

e) Improvement rate, ESF_i : measures the distance between the current evaluation of each function and the desired one:

$$\Delta F_i = TF_i - EF_i$$

f) Negative values point out those functions to improve. While nulls (or positive) values point out that we reached (or overcome) the target.

g) Impact on customer: for each function its improvement rate is multiplied for its importance. In this way, it's clearer the impact of the actual state of our product on customer perception.

h) Relative weight: shows the preceding operation in percentage.

i) Correlation between functions, R_{ij} in this matrix, built up by interfunctional team of the firm, the values take on by correlations, rf_{ij} are included in a range between [-1,1]. We have already seen that knowing the degree of correlation is very useful. In fact, the existence of a positive correlation could mean redundancy, while a negative one incompatibility.

j) Covering rate: through the data contained in the relationships matrix, the program calculates for each function the number of components to which it is tied up and the type of the existing relationships. As we consider that the importance of a function could depend on both the strength and the number of its relationship.

Figure 2. Functions' Importance

3.3 Components (C_j)

In this mask we insert all the information gathered on the components of our product, which allows us to make a powerful comparison between company's products and those of the competitors.

Following, we see more in detail the data contained, giving a brief explanation of their origin.

a) Weight of significance: they are the same of the preceding mask, they are still referred to functions, since also the components are weighted on the functions they are linked to.

b) Importance, IC_j : for each column of the relationships matrix, corresponding to a component of the product, the program multiplies its elements (the correspondent numerical values of the linguistics label) for the associated function importance:

$$IC_j = \sum_{MI} (9t, xW_i)$$

Each of these values is a measure of the real weight of a certain component inside the product.

c) Current evaluation: like for functions, the current state of the components of our product must be evaluated. These evaluations are given from internal people of the firm.

d) Target: through a comparison with competitors' products, we settle a level to reach for each component of our product.

e) Distance, AC_j : it measures the distance between the current evaluation of a component and its objective.

f) Technical difficulty, $d(C_j)$: it is an evaluation made from production engineers about the difficulty of realization of each component.

g) Technical importance, $IT(C_j)$: to better understand how each component distance influences the product, the software multiplies for each component its difficulty, $d(C_j)$, for its importance value, IC_j .

h) Relative Importance: considering the preceding step the relative importance of the components is calculated in terms of percentage.

i) Correlation between components, IRC: as we did before for functions, a correlation matrix is built to underline the type of bonds between different components of the same system (see Figure 3). The existence of negative relationships between two components means they are incompatible. This will force the system to seek a compromise in the solution.

j) Covering rate: this chart shows the number and the strength of the relationships of each component.

Figure 3. Correlation Matrix between Components

3.4 Costs

At this point we need component costs, $s(C_j)$, and the total budget constrain, B , we are allowed to spend. With these new data the algorithm can choose those components of the product, that, improved increase its competitiveness, as they improve, from customer point of view, the level of satisfaction of the functions supported by the product.

Then, to reach our objective, we introduce the following hypothesis:

All the components can be improved:

$$AC_j < 0 \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

The cost $s(C_j)$ represents the necessary increase of cost for the component j to reach its target:

$$s(C_j) = AC_j - 0 \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

The budget constrain, B is the sum of two shares:

$$\bar{B} = AB + B$$

where AB is the total amount of money increase of money that the firm has arranged to invest in product's improvements and B is the amount of money invested for the current product. Therefore, our optimization concerns only, AB , while B doesn't enter in the optimization process, we can't act on it because it represents the necessary amount to realize the basic model of the product (it was already spent).

Following, we introduce the improvement cost for each component, $s(C_j)$, supposing that its estimation is made basing on current cost, $s(C_j)$, technical difficulty, $cf(C^*)$ and distance from the target AC_j :

$$s(C_j) = f(j(C_j), AC_j, rf(C_j))$$

3.5 Functions and components ordering

Now, we dispose of all necessary information to plan product design strategies. In fact, from one side, we have the data relative to customer needs and, from the other, that relative to the current state of our product. With this mask the program carries out a thorough analysis of the product requirements with greater specific weighting for the client and the way the company is positioned within these requirements regarding its competitors. This is carried out through the definition of a matrix, as is shown in figure 4, where both variables of the strategic management can be crossed. Analyzes the data and gives us the guidelines.

Figure 4. Strategic matrix

Once the matrix has been built, it is possible to carry out analysis by quadrants identifying the critical points or priority improvements. In this case it is possible to define four categories or main situations:

Winners (functions highly weighted with competitive evaluation): They are consumer's requirements over which the company has a certain market power. However, investment in them must be carried out to maintain the dominant position.

Opportunities (functions highly weighted with low competitive evaluation): unlike the previous case, it shows a company's bad position, which supposes a critical point or a priority improvement opportunity.

Sleepers (functions downwardly weighted with high competitive evaluation): Although the company has a good position in the market they are low interest or deadlocked requirements, that is, they could provide volume but not activity growth.

Questionable (functions downwardly weighted with low competitive evaluation): in this case neither the requirement shows a future business opportunity nor the company is especially well situated in the market. So, they are possible candidates for elimination, to be subcontracted or without further investment, depending on the role they play on the final product.

In short, with this matrix information about the items in which the company should focus its efforts or resources could be obtained, focusing especially on those which suppose important growth opportunities but where there is still not a market quota similar to other requirements also demanded by the consumers (bad position in the market). Those items so-called sleepers could also be known, where efforts are made in a sterile direction as they are stagnant or have a decreasing interest for consumers and whose investment needs can be less.

3.6 The model of Genetic Algorithm developed

In this mask we get the necessary parameters for genetic algorithm implementation.

Data of the genetic algorithm:

- a) Percentage of crossover, p_c : we settle the percentage of individuals of the actual population that will be subject to crossover, for each generation. This percentage randomly changes in a certain range, $p_c \in [p_{c1}, p_{c2}]$, it is not a determined number.
- b) Percentage of mutation, p_m : we settle the percentage of individuals of the actual population that will be subject to the mutation, for each generation. Also this percentage randomly changes in a range, $p_m \in [p_{m1}, p_{m2}]$.
- c) Number of generations, n^{gen} : one this parameter is fixed, the convergence criteria is chosen. That is, the number of generations the algorithm will create before finding the best solution.
- d) Population size, n^{gen} : it is the number of individuals belonging to the population, at each generation.

Beyond to the necessary parameters for the right working of the algorithm, there are some buttons to start the simulation that will work on the information gathered in the preceding masks. And, naturally, there is also the button to visualize the gotten solution.

Figure 5. Genetic Algorithm Mask

4 Analysis of the points of strength and of weakness results interpretation

Above we show the information needed by the algorithm and the mechanisms chosen for its implementation. Now, we analyze the differences that we verified between two different simulations of the genetic algorithm.

The data of the masks and the parameters of the genetic algorithm (p_m, p_c, \dots) will be the same for both simulations, the only difference concerns the budget constrain. In fact, in the first case we will propose a budget of $=2.000$, while for the second of $AB_2 = 1.400$.

The simulations are characterized by the following parameters:

$$0.5 \leq p_c \leq 0.6 \quad n^{gen} = 30$$

$$0.2 \leq p_{ff} \leq 0.3 \quad \lambda = 20$$

Each individual, P_i solution of the algorithm, is valued through two variables:

- 1- $f(P^*)$ its fitness.
- 2. $NC(P^*)$, number of included components in the individual, of course with $0 \leq NC(P^*) \leq h$

In the first case we have a budget constrain of $AB_1 = 2.000$, that being a little bit inferior to total cost of the components, $S_{Tot} = \sum_{i=1}^{17} C_i = 3.218$, allows selecting a concept with almost all the components. From Figure 6 we notices that of the seventeen existing components sixteen were introduced, with a fitness value little superior to 14:

Figure 6. Solution case n° 1

We analyze, instead, the results of the second example. The budget, $AB_2 = 1.400$, is very more restrictive than the first, it carries to a final concept constituted from 8 components with a fitness value around 13.

Figure 7. Solution case n° 2

Comparing the two results we notice that, they differ for the number of components, 9 in the first 8 in the second, and for the fitness of the best individual, 14 and 13. This result depends, obviously, on budget constrain. Now we want to show that the value of $f(P_2)$, obtained in the second simulation doesn't depend, entirely, on budget constrain. For this reason we make, for the second example, another simulation with these parameters:

$$0.5_j Sp_c \text{ £} 0.6 \quad n^{\circ} gen = 50$$

$$0.2 \phi_m IS 0.3 \quad W = 20$$

With these new parameters, in which we have only increased the number of generations, we arrived to a new fitness value, nearly 14, better than that of the preceding simulation. This means that when budget constrain is more restrictive we must allow the algorithm to create more generations to reach the best solution.

Let's analyze the results of the two examples and with a extreme case without budget constrain:

	Example 1	Example 2	Distance	Extreme case	Increased percentage
Cost	2.000	1.400	600	3218	18,6%
Fitness	14,0	13,0	1	20	4%

The increased percentages are calculated as difference of first two examples on values of extreme case, in which budget constrain is equal to total improvement costs of all the components.

The interesting result, which we draw from the cost/fitness curve, allows us to establish until which point is convenient to increase improvement cost.

In fact, the relationship cost/fitness is proportional only for a part of the curve. Until we are on this pull, it would be opportune to increase the budget for improvements. After this point it would not be worthwhile to increase it because great budget increases would correspond very little increases of fitness.

Figure 8. Cost/Fitness curve

5 Conclusions and future lines

In this article we show the real applicability of genetic algorithms techniques to design product processes. We could affirm that through this software we have, really, the possibility of make powerful improvements for new products, basing customer's preferences. Naturally, for an effectiveness use of the software, we still have to work on some of its aspects.

We have analyzed the necessary data to the implement the simulations and the solutions reached. We show, therefore, the operational validity of the use of the genetic algorithms in this type of application.

The great problem lays once more, in data robustness: the genetic algorithm works correctly once truthful data are introduced. But, we know we are working in fields where uncertainty degree is very high, for which rises the problem of the inadequacy of the use of numerical scales to evaluation the information gathered. That's why we are working to introduce fuzzy techniques for data interpretation. In this way would be possible working without eliminating existing uncertainty.

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